

Harvest data from two fields showed spraying increased yield 7.3 and 10% over the control.

More than 25,000 stems were dissected to determine the correlation between YSB infested stems at harvest and yield. Mean infestation was 27 to 60%, but no consistently significant correlations were found, perhaps because the stems dissected were less than 1% of the field population or because a younger crop is more sensitive to YSB damage (sampling was done at harvest).

We recorded and analyzed YSB infestation and grain sterility of the stems taken at harvest. Varieties differed in the internode most sensitive to damage. In variety Chamara despite 90% infestation (n = 254), grain loss was not significant unless the top internode was infested. In variety Sada Pankaish at lower infestation

Effect of monocrotophos (250g ai/ha) spray on YSB in deepwater rice. Dubail (Tangail) and DND Project area, Dhaka, 1982.^a

Variety	Whitehead (%)		Infested stem (%)	
	Unsprayed	Sprayed	Unsprayed	Sprayed
Dubail				
Sonna digha	8.6	8.6 ns	74.6	50.5**
Chamara	5.9	2.1 **	58.0	28.2**
Boron Bawalia	10.8	2.4 **	54.0	21.0**
Sonna digha	8.2	6.1 ns	48.0	33.3*
Boron Bawalia	11.0	3.5 **	63.0	38.0**
DND				
Khama	10.3	4.7 **	57.0	45.0 ns
Khama	12.7	4.6 **	52.8	32.0**
Khama	11.8	6.3 **	70.0	59.1 ns

^aThe difference between sprayed and unsprayed areas, compared by t-test, are indicated as ns = not significant, * = significant at 5% level, and ** = significant at 1% level.

levels (37%, n = 254), infestation in either the 1st, 3d, or 4th top internodes could significantly reduce grain filling. But in both varieties, whiteheads in the top internode caused greatest yield loss.

This result was verified in another

study where varieties Chamara and Boron Bawalia showed that 94% of stems with whiteheads were infested in the top internode (n = 205) but few whiteheads were associated with infestation at the lower internodes (down to the 6th internode). □

Rice gall midge (GM) (*Orseolia oryzae* Wood-Mason) biotypes in Guangdong Province

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GM is one of the most serious pests in South China. It is found in the mountain region, in some hilly areas, and in the central plains of Guangdong Province. Biotype studies were made in 1979-83

Adults are collected from the overwintering generation that infests the wild host plant *Leersia hexandra* and

from infested rice at different sites. Damaged plants are put in pots in cages for symptom development. Adult insects are collected from the damaged plants and used to infest differential varieties.

To test for different biotypes we used Leaug 152, OB677, IET2911, W1263, Ptb21, and Muey Nahng 62M from IRRI. They were tested in 16 representative

Reactions of differential rice varieties to GM biotypes at various sites in Guangdong Province, China.

Location	Category ^a	China GM biotype	Differential reaction ^b to GM						
			Leaug 152	OB677	IET2911	W1263	Ptb21	Muey Nahng 62M	
Guangzhou region	Huaxian	H	I	MR	MR	MR	MR	S	S
	Songhua	M	I	R	MR	R	MR	S	-
	Pengyu	P	II	R	R	R	S	S	S
Fozan region	Nanhai	P	II	R	R	R	S	S	S
	Xinhui	H	II	R	R	R	S	S	-
	Sanshui	P	II	R	MR	R	S	S	-
	Zhongzan	P	II	R	MR	R	S	S	-
Zantou region	Chaoan	P	II	R	MR	R	S	S	S
Huiyang region	Huizhou	H	II	R	MR	MR	S	S	S
	Dongwan	P	I	R	R	R	MR	S	S
Shaoguan region	Shaoguan	M	I	R	R	R	R	S	S
	Lianshan	M	III	S	S	S	R	S	S
Meixian region	Meixian	M	IV	S	S	S	S	S	S
	Wuhua	M	IV	S	S	S	S	S	-
Shaoqing region	Fenkai	M	IV	S	S	S	S	S	S
Zhanjiang region	Xinyi	M	IV	S	S	S	S	S	S

^a H = hilly area, M = mountain region, P = plain. ^b MR = moderately resistant, R = resistant, S = susceptible.

localities in Guangdong: Huaxian, Songhua, Zhaozuan, Dongwan, Nanhai, Sanshui, Xinhui, Zhongzan, Pengyu, Huiyan, Chaoan, Lianshan, Fenkai,

Xinyi, Meixian, and Wuhua. Experiments were repeated many times. The GM populations were classified according to varietal reaction.

Reactions of the differential varieties to GM differed among locations. Results indicated there are at least four GM biotypes in the province (see table). □

Detection of enzyme polymorphism among populations of brown planthopper (BPH) biotypes

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We found horizontal starch gel electrophoresis useful for surveying enzyme polymorphism among BPH biotypes.

The procedure has three steps.

1. *Preparation of enzyme crude extracts.* Newly emerged male and female BPH biotype 1, 2, and 3 were obtained from stock cultures and frozen at -20°C for at least 2 h before electrophoresis. Individual hoppers were placed in depressions on a spot plate and ground in $15\ \mu\text{l}$ of the homogenizing solution (0.05M tris-histidine buffer, pH 8) using a glass rod. Whatman filter paper no. 3 bits ($4\ \text{mm} \times 9\ \text{mm}$) were used to adsorb the crude extract and were inserted directly into the appropriate gel.
2. *Electrophoresis.* Standard horizontal starch gel electrophoresis was used. The starch gel (14%, Electro-starch) was prepared using 0.05M tris-histidine buffer pH 8 and was used to resolve all the enzymes except esterase, which separated more clearly at pH 6. Tris-citrate (0.4M, pH 8) was the electrode buffer, and was adjusted to pH 6 for esterase. Electrophoresis was conducted for 4 h in a refrigerator ($0-4^{\circ}\text{C}$) at about 30 mA/gel slab. An ice pack was placed on top of the gel during electrophoresis; afterward, the gel was sliced horizontally into several sheets and stained.
3. *Histochemical staining.* We used the following enzyme assays. *Alcohol*

Enzymes investigated after horizontal starch gel electrophoresis. IRRI, 1983.

Locus	Enzyme activity ^a	Gene loci (no.)	Isoenzymes (maximum no.)	Migration
<i>Polymorphic</i>				
Catalase	+	1	2	Anodal
Esterase	+	3	6	Anodal
Isocitrate dehydrogenase	+	1	3	Anodal
Malate dehydrogenase	+	1	3	Anodal
Malic enzyme	+	1	4	Anodal
Phosphoglucose isomerase	+	2	8	Anodal
<i>Monomorphic</i>				
Acid phosphatase	+	1 or 2	2	Cathodal
Glucose kinase	+	1	1	Anodal
Glucosed-6-phosphate dehydrogenase	+	1 or 2	2	Anodal
Leucine aminopeptidase	+	1	1	Anodal
Phosphogluconate dehydrogenase	+	1 or 2	2	Anodal
Alcohol dehydrogenase	-			
Glutamate dehydrogenase	-			
Glutamate-oxaloacetate mutase	-			
Lactate dehydrogenase	-			
Peroxidase	-			
Shikimate dehydrogenase	-			
Tetrazolium oxidase	-			

^a+ = present, - = not detected.

dehydrogenase (Adh): 1 mg PMS, 10 mg NBT, 10 mg NAD, 0.25 ml EtOH in 50 ml 0.05M tris-HCl buffer, pH 8.5, incubate gel for 30 min at 24°C . *Leucyl aminopeptidase (Lap):* 25 mg leucyl- β -naphthyl in 5 ml $\text{N}_2\text{N}'$ -dimethyl formamide, 25 mg FBK salt, 25 ml tris-maleate buffer (0.2M, pH 3.3), 20 ml NaOH (0.1 M), incubate gel for 30 min at 40°C . *Acid phosphatase (AcPh):* 50 mg Fast garnet GBC, 50 mg α -naphthyl acid phosphate, 0.5 ml MgCl_2 (0.1M), 50 ml acetate buffer (0.2M, pH 4), incubate gel overnight at 24°C . *Catalase (Cat):* 50 ml H_2O_2 (7%) solution, incubate gel for 3 min, then wash with tap water, pour 50 ml KI solution (0.09M) with a drop of acetic acid. *Esterase (Est):* 50 mg α -naphthyl acetate, 10 mg Fast blue RR, 10 mg Fast garnet GBC in 50 ml phosphate buffer (0.1 M, pH 6.5), incubate gel for 15 min at 40°C . *Glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (Gpd):* 1 mg PMS,

10 mg NBT, 5 mg NADP, 2 ml MgCl_2 (0.1M), 100 mg glucose-6-phosphate in 50 ml 0.05M tris-HCl buffer, pH 8.5, incubate gel for 30 min at 24°C . *Glutamate dehydrogenase (Gdh):* 250 mg sodium glutamate, 10 mg NAD, 10 mg NBT, 1 mg PMS in 50 ml 0.05M tris-HCl buffer, pH 8.5, incubate gel for 30 min at 24°C . *Glutamate oxaloacetate transaminase (Got):* 200 mg aspartic acid, 100 mg α -ketoglutaric acid, 1 mg pyridoxal 5, phosphate, 200 mg Fast blue BB salt in 50 ml 0.05M tris-HCl buffer, pH 8.5, incubate gel for 30 min at 24°C . *Isocitrate dehydrogenase (Idh):* 100 mg isocitrate tri-sodium, 5 mg NADP, 10 mg NBT, 1 mg PMS, 2 ml MgCl_2 (0.1M) in 0.05M tris-HCl buffer, pH 8.5. *Lactate dehydrogenase (Ldh):* 1 mg PMS, 10 mg NBT, 10 mg NAD, 1M/80 lilactate in 0.05M tris-HCl buffer, pH 8.5, incubate gel for 30 min at 24°C . *Malate dehydrogenase (Mdh):* 1 mg